

Supplementary Material

An optimization framework for task allocation in the edge/hub/cloud paradigm

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Appendix A

Table A.1: List of notations used in the proposed framework.

Notation	Definition
\mathcal{T}	Set of tasks of the considered application.
\mathcal{U}	Set of computational devices in the target system.
\mathcal{F}_i	Subset of computational devices where task i can be allocated ($\mathcal{F}_i \subseteq \mathcal{U}$).
i, j	Tasks of the considered application ($i, j \in \mathcal{T}$).
k, l, m	Computational devices in the target system ($k, l, m \in \mathcal{U}$).
$G = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A})$	Task flow graph (TFG) of the considered application.
\mathcal{N}	Set of nodes in the TFG.
\mathcal{A}	Set of arcs in the TFG.
N_i	Node in the TFG ($N_i \in \mathcal{N}$) corresponding to task $i \in \mathcal{T}$.
$A_{i \rightarrow j}$	Arc in the TFG ($A_{i \rightarrow j} \in \mathcal{A}$) connecting nodes N_i and N_j .
$G' = (\mathcal{N}', \mathcal{A}')$	Extended task flow graph (ETFG) of the considered application.
f_{node}	Function that transforms a node $N_i \in G$ into a composite node $N'_i \in G'$.
f_{arc}	Function that transforms an arc $A_{i \rightarrow j} \in G$ into a composite arc $A'_{i \rightarrow j} \in G'$.
\mathcal{N}'	Set of composite nodes in the ETFG.
\mathcal{A}'	Set of composite arcs in the ETFG.
N'_i	Composite node in the ETFG ($N'_i \in \mathcal{N}'$) comprising a set of candidate nodes N_{ik} .
N_{ik}	Candidate node in N'_i corresponding to the allocation of task i on device k .
$A'_{i \rightarrow j}$	Composite arc in the ETFG ($A'_{i \rightarrow j} \in \mathcal{A}'$) comprising a set of arcs $A_{ik \rightarrow jl}$.
$A_{ik \rightarrow jl}$	Arc in $A'_{i \rightarrow j}$ corresponding to the data flow between candidate nodes N_{ik} and N_{jl} .
L_{ik}	Computational latency (execution time) of task i on device k .
P_{ik}	Computational power consumption required to execute task i on device k .
E_{ik}	Computational energy consumption required to execute task i on device k .
M_i	Main memory requirement of task i .
S_i	Storage requirement of task i .
D_i	Output data size of task i .
NC_i	Number of child tasks of task i .
$CL_{ik \rightarrow jl}$	Communication latency of arc $A_{ik \rightarrow jl}$.
$CE_{ik \rightarrow jl}$	Communication energy consumption of arc $A_{ik \rightarrow jl}$.
$\delta_{ik \rightarrow jl}^m$	Binary parameter denoting whether arc $A_{ik \rightarrow jl}$ involves indirect communication through device m .
W_{kl}	Bandwidth of communication channel between devices k and l .
τ_{kl}	Energy required to transmit a unit of data from device k to device l .
ρ_{kl}	Energy required to receive a unit of data at device l from device k .
x_{ik}	Binary decision variable corresponding to candidate node N_{ik} .
$x_{ik \rightarrow jl}$	Binary decision variable corresponding to arc $A_{ik \rightarrow jl}$.
M_k^{bgt}	Memory budget corresponding to device k .
S_k^{bgt}	Storage budget corresponding to device k .
E_k^{bgt}	Energy budget corresponding to device k .
L_{thr}	Overall latency threshold.
ϕ_k	Performance ratio of device k for a specific device benchmark with respect to reference device \hat{e} .*
ϕ_k^{avg}	Average performance ratio of device k across all device benchmarks with respect to reference device \hat{e} .*
P_k^{idle}	Idle power consumption of device k .*
P_k^{max}	Maximum power consumption of device k .*
α	Adjustment factor of computational power consumption.*

*Used in the transformation of random TFGs into ETFGs.

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(a) Flowchart of the application encapsulating its TFG

(b) Corresponding ETFG

Figure A.1: Real-world use-case application: (a) its flowchart that encapsulates its TFG, and (b) its corresponding ETFG.